

THE IMPACT OF PTERYGIUM SURGICAL EXCISION ON CORNEAL ASTIGMATISM

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Abstract

Background: Pterygium is the lesion that grows on the ocular surface. It is described as the elastotic degeneration of the collagen and proliferation of fibro-vascular mass, along with the overlying layer of conjunctival epithelium. Pterygium causes the corneal alteration and induces the significant volume of astigmatism. Excision of pterygium is the surgical procedure which can help to retrieve the corneal astigmatism to the normal.

Objective: To find the mean change in astigmatism after pterygium excision in the adult population.

Material & methods: This Quasi experimental study was done at Department of Ophthalmology, Services Hospital, Lahore for 6months. Thirty five patients filling the inclusion criteria were registered. A preoperative keratometry was performed. All patients underwent Pterygium excision with autologous conjunctival graft and postoperative keratometric readings were taken at one month follow-up. Change in the corneal astigmatism was recorded. All data was collected by using a proforma. SPSS v. 17 was used for data analysis.

Results: The mean age of patients was 43.49 ± 16.02 years. There were 26 (74.3%) males while 9 (25.7%) females. At baseline, the mean astigmatism was $4.06 \pm 1.04D$ which was reduced to $2.92 \pm 0.93D$ after surgery. The mean change in astigmatism was $1.14 \pm 0.23D$. This was significant decrease in astigmatism after surgery ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Thus, pterygium excision is beneficial in reducing corneal astigmatism in adults.

Keywords: Astigmatism, pterygium excision, diopter, autologous conjunctival graft

Pterygium is derived from a Greek word “pterygos” which means “wing”. It is commonly present as a lesion on the ocular surface and described as the elastotic degeneration of the collagen material and proliferation of fibro vascular mass, along with the covering of the epithelium lie on the top.¹ It grows in the inter-palpebral space which most frequently affects the nasal side of palpebral conjunctiva. Even though, pathogenesis of the Pterygium is not clear yet, but it is supposed that the ultraviolet radiations can be a significant and strongest influencing factor for development of pterygium, in addition to the dry

eyes or person is living in a hot warm climate.² Lately, it was opposed that the mutations in gene p53 present on the chromosome 17 might be responsible for development of Pterygium.²

According to the distribution, the chances of Pterygium are twice among males as compared to females. This may be because of excessive outdoor exposure of the males is more than females which raises the probability of Pterygium among males.² Patients having pterygium present with the wide range of complaints. Sometimes it is asymptomatic while sometime it cause severe symptoms like

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redness, along with itching, reduced ocular motility and reduced or blurred vision.³ The effect of pterygium on the status of the corneal refraction can be estimated by using refraction, keratometry & corneal topography.⁴ Pterygium causes the alteration in the cornea and also persuades the significant extent of the astigmatism. In a study done by Faisal Aziz Khan, astigmatism may occur either due to pooling of tears in advance of the pterygium or by traction generated by the pterygium mechanically pulling on and distorting the cornea or both.⁴

The most common indications for the excision of Pterygium are: reduction in the vision because of intrusion on the visual axis as well as due to altered astigmatism level, old irritation in the eye, recurrence of inflammation, obstructive ocular motility and also the cosmetic purposes.⁵ Several surgical methods have already been described. These methods include the “bare sclera excision with or without using adjuncts like beta radiation, thiotepa eye drops, intra-operative or post-operative application of mitomycin C, amniotic membrane transplant and conjunctival autograft.”⁵⁻⁷ This study was aimed to find mean change in astigmatism after pterygium excision. This study would help us in guiding patients about the possible outcome of the surgery and assess the outcome of pterygium surgery in our population. Objective was to find the mean change in corneal astigmatism after pterygium surgical excision in adult population.

METHODOLOGY

Study design: Quasi experimental trial

Venue: Department of Ophthalmology, Services Hospital, Lahore.

Duration of study: Six months i.e. from December 01, 2015 to May 30, 2016.

Sample size: Sample size = 35 cases is estimated by keeping 95% confidence level, $d=0.12$ and taking expected mean $\pm$ SD of mean decrease in corneal astigmatism i.e. 0.95 ± 0.34 after pterygium excision in adult population.

Sampling technique: Patients were recruited via Non-probability, consecutive sampling

Selection Criteria: All patients with age range of 20-70 years of either gender with primary pterygium, defined as triangular fibro vascular ingrowth of bulbar conjunctiva over the limbus onto the cornea involving ≥ 1 mm of cornea measured on slit lamp examination were included. Patients with recurrent pterygium, having corneal pathology like keratoconus, corneal opacity or any previous ocular surgery diagnosed on history and slit lamp examination were excluded.

Data Collection Procedure: The written informed consent was acquired from all patients. After obtaining ocular and systemic history, ocular inspection was done in affected eye including the estimation of visual acuity on Snellen’s chart, manifest refraction and slit lamp anterior segment examination. A preoperative keratometric reading was taken by an automated keratometer (Nikon keratometric). All patients then underwent Pterygium excision with autologous conjunctival graft and postoperative keratometric reading was taken at one month follow-up.

Change in Astigmatism: Irregular curvature of the cornea due to pterygium assessed in Diopter (D) by keratometry at preoperative and one month postoperative. Difference in preoperative and postoperative astigmatism readings in Diopter (D)

Data Analysis: The collected data was analyzed by using software SPSS version 17. The frequency and percentage was calculated for gender. The quantitative data including age, preoperative and postoperative astigmatism and change in astigmatism were presented as mean and standard deviation. Paired t-test was applied to determine the mean change in astigmatism keeping p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant cut-off.

RESULTS

The mean age of patients was 43.49 ± 16.02 years. There were 26 (74.3%) males while 9 (25.7%) females. About 17 (48.6%) patients had issue in the

right eye while 18 (51.4%) patients had problem in left eye. Table1

At baseline, the mean astigmatism was 4.06 ± 1.04 D which was reduced to 2.92 ± 0.93 D after surgery. The mean change in astigmatism was 1.14 ± 0.23 D. There was significant decrease in astigmatism after surgery ($p < 0.05$). Table2

DISCUSSION

Pterygium is an ocular disorder which can significantly alter the refractive astigmatism, that in turn results in significant deterioration of the vision.⁸ In our study, at baseline, the mean astigmatism was 4.06 ± 1.04 D which was reduced to 2.92 ± 0.93 D after surgery. The mean change in astigmatism was 1.14 ± 0.23 D. There was significant decrease in astigmatism after surgery ($p < 0.05$).

In a local study done by Khan et al., the pre-operative astigmatism was 2.25D which was reduced

measured with automated keratometer.⁴ In another study by Eknath Shalke in India the mean decrease in corneal astigmatism was up to 2.66 ± 0.075 D which is much greater than the mean decrease in astigmatism in this local study i.e. 0.95 D.⁹

The reduction in the astigmatism level after surgical excision was dependent on the size of the pterygium, which was surgically removed.¹⁰ Various authors have reported variable amount of astigmatism by comparing the length of pterygium using corneal topography. Pterygium which are < 2.5 mm induce less astigmatism of 1.25 D compared to those > 2.5 mm which induce on average 3.94 D of astigmatism.¹¹

Hansen et al. reported that pterygium > 3.0 mm induced 1.97 D of astigmatism versus 1.11 D in < 3 mm.¹² Kampitak reported a 2 D or more of astigmatism with length greater than 2.25 mm.¹³ Recently, Jaffar et al. found a strong correlation with a mean size of 2.84 ± 0.557 mm and inducing a 3.46 ± 1.441 D ($p = 0.01$) of astigmatism.¹⁴ On the contrary, Fong et al. results did not accord with other studies who found that pterygium had to be greater than 3.5 mm to induce 1 D of astigmatism.¹⁵

Maheshwari et al., found that the pre-operative refractive astigmatism was reduced from 4.60 ± 2 D to 2.20 ± 2.04 D, post-operatively. This was a significant reduction in level of astigmatism ($P = 0.00001$).⁸ Vives et al., also found that there was significant reduction in astigmatism after excision i.e. the mean pre-operative astigmatism was 1.8 ± 1.35 D, which was reduced to 1.15 ± 0.9 D after one month of excision while further reduced to 1 ± 0.46 D after three months of the excision. There was also significant correlation obtained between the length of pterygium and pre-operative astigmatism level ($p < 0.05$).¹⁶

In another study, conducted by Cinal et al., excision was done in 27 patients. It was found that pre-operative astigmatism at 3 mm pterygium length was 2.30 ± 2.08 D which was reduced to 0.82 ± 0.74 D after excision. This reduction was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$).¹⁷ Soriano et al., also found

Table 1: Demographics of Patients

n	35
Age (years)	43.49±16.02
Gender	
Male	26 (74.3%)
Female	9 (25.7%)
Anatomical Side	
Right	17(48.57%)
Left	18(51.43%)

Table 2: Change in Astigmatism before and after Treatment

	Preoperative	Postoperative	Change	P-value
Astigmatism (D)	4.06 ± 1.04	2.92 ± 0.93	1.14 ± 0.23	< 0.05

ced to 1.30 ± 0.22 D post-operative astigmatism. This reduction in the post-operative astigmatism level was observed to be statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). There is a mean decrease of 0.95 D in corneal astigmatism after pterygium surgery. After removal there is a significant influence on the corneal refractive parameters which includes spherical power, astigmatism, asymmetry and irregularity. This decrease in corneal astigmatism is statistically significant when

that there is a significant decrease in the central corneal astigmatism i.e. from 2.41 D to 1.29 D after excision of pterygium regardless of the small sample size of the research work.¹⁹ But Bahar et al., reported an insignificant reduction of astigmatism i.e. 3.12D to 2.50D after excision of pterygium, without any changes in the axis.¹⁸

CONCLUSION

Pterygium excision is beneficial in reducing the corneal astigmatism in adults. We can recommend this method to improve astigmatism in patients of pterygium.

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